

Brand Image, Customer Engagement, and Web Design Quality: Their Influence toward Online Repurchase Intentions

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Abstract

This research focuses on the role of brands in increasing repurchase intention through good relationships and trust formed with consumers. This study aimed to examine and analyze the effect of brand image, customer involvement, and web design quality on online repurchase intentions, in this case, for hotel reservations in the traveloka application through the mediation of electronic trust. The population used in this study are consumers who have made hotel reservations using the Traveloka application in Malang- Indonesia. The sampling technique in this study was purposive sampling. The sample used in this study was 170 respondents. The analytical method used in this study is Partial Least Square (PLS) using the Smart Modeling Partial Least Squares application. The results showed that the three independent variables, namely brand image, customer involvement, web design quality, and the electronic trust mediation variable, had a significant effect on online repurchase intentions for hotel reservations in the application. They also significantly affect electronic trust. Moreover, electronic trust can provide a Partial mediation role (partially mediate) in the relationship between brand image, customer involvement, and web design quality on online repurchase intentions for hotel reservations in the traveloka application.

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1. Introduction

Information technology plays a significant role in the current era of globalization. Information, communication, and internet technologies have penetrated various areas of life, including business and trade. The development of technology and the internet gave birth to network businesses or online shops, making it easier for consumers to get the goods or services they want. In the field of commerce, information technology is better known as electronic commerce or e-commerce. E-commerce (electronic commerce) is part of electronic business (business conducted using electronic transmission). E-Commerce means that companies or online sites offer to facilitate the sale of products and services online or when making transactions (Ivoni, D., I. W. & Alit, 2015). Likewise, e-marketing describes companies that inform, communicate, promote to buyers, and sell their products and services via the internet. (Megantara, I., M. & Alit, 2016).

According to (Sunarto, R. 2014) in-demand theory, several factors influence demand, one of which is income. The average income of consumers is a significant factor in determining the pattern of demand for various goods. People's consumption patterns will shift when their education and income increase (S., 2019). Changes in income always cause changes in the demand for various types of goods or services. Based on the nature of the change in need, it applies when income changes. Various goods or services can be divided into four categories: inferior goods, essential goods, everyday goods, and luxury goods. Several indicators are used to see how much the average income is and how high the level of people's prosperity is; one indicator is per capita domestic product (per capita income). The term per capita income is used to describe the result of dividing gross domestic product divided by the population (Sunarto, R., 2014).

Several factors affect demand, namely the price of the goods or services themselves, the prices of other goods or services, household income, the style of the income distribution, the taste of society, population, and predictions about conditions in the future. Increasing per capita income means consumers' ability to consume, make requests, drink, or buy goods & services will increase. Also, consumers can enjoy better quality goods and services. So when it comes to hospitality services, when per capita income increases, then automatically, the ability of the community to use hospitality services will increase, and in turn, the district has the choice to choose better hospitality services than before their income increased (Sunarto, R., 2014).

Citing data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (2017) in Figure 1, the data states that in 2015-2017 there was a significant increase in entertainment needs. On the other hand, spending on basic needs, especially food, has decreased. Statistically, the average cost of entertainment (per capita per month) during 2015-2017 rose 30.96 percent. Meanwhile, staple food spending fell by 2.9 percent. During 2015-2017, when seen in figure 1., spending on entertainment doubled. Meanwhile, spending on basic food needs has decreased. According to data from the National Socioeconomic Survey from the Central Bureau of Statistics (2017), the average cost of entertainment (per capita per month) during 2015-2017 rose by 30.96 percent. Meanwhile, spending on staple foods fell by 2.97 percent. DKI Jakarta has the most significant ratio: 0.127. Every month, residents of DKI Jakarta spend an average of IDR 7,149 for entertainment. As for staple food, Rp. 56,379 was issued. The province with the smallest ratio is East Nusa Tenggara, with only 0.002 times spending on staple food. Understandably, they spend Rp. 112,275 for staple food. While entertainment costs only need Rp. 249. In the context of figure 1 also shows a symptom of a change in the economy's direction from which was previously reliant on the goods production sector to the entertainment or pleasure service sector. The contemporary economic theory calls it the leisure economy.

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics, 2017

Figure 1. Comparison of Entertainment Costs to Staple Food Expenditure

This shift in consumption patterns towards the leisure economy occurs in almost all countries with higher middle-class growth rates. This fact, at the same time, reinforces the premise that the leisure economy and the middle class are interrelated phenomena and cannot be separated (Hidayah, S., 2019). Significant growth of the middle class has also occurred in Indonesia. Referring to the Asian Development Bank (ADB) criteria in (Hidayah, S., 2019) which defines the middle class with a per-capita expenditure range per day of US\$2-20, the middle class in Indonesia currently reaches 134 million people. This number will likely continue to increase when looking at the trends and trends that have surfaced recently. More than 70 percent of millennials, according to the Haris Group study in (Zahrotustianah & Rintan, 2019) prefer to spend on an 'experience' rather than 'objects.' Many things characterize the middle class. One of them is its unique consumption behavior. The middle class tends to allocate their expenses for needs that are both pleasure and experience, apart from being identified as a group with relatively high consumption rates. Tourism, hotel, culinary, film, music performance, and industries related to the leisure economy have developed quite rapidly in recent years. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the future of the leisure economy in Indonesia is auspicious by looking at the growing middle class and hotels taking advantage of increasingly sophisticated information technology developments (Hidayah, S., 2019).

Table 1
Development of Number of Indonesian Guests in Star-rated Hotels in the 2003-2012 Period

Year	Number of Indonesian Guests at Star Hotels (in thousands)
2003	10581.90
2004	11682.20
2005	11610.30
2006	11659.30
2007	13113.20
2008	14358.50
2009	17212.70

Table 2
Development of Indonesia's Number of Star-Hotel Guests in the 2003-2012 Period

Year	Number of Indonesian Guests at Star Hotels (in thousands)
2010	18560.20
2011	22672.40
2012	24802.90

Source: Sunarto et al., 2014

According to research by Sunarto, R. (2014), per capita income and inflation simultaneously affect the hotel industry, especially the number of Indonesian guests at star hotels 2003-2012 period. Per capita income had a positive and significant effect on the number of Indonesian guests at star hotels in the 2003-2012 period, which can be seen in Table 1 and Table 2. The growth in the hotel restaurant sector is also related to the increase in transportation support applications, such as Traveloka, Tiket.com, Go-Jek, etc. This new consumer class is interested in the restaurant business, which is packaged creatively, as well as budget hotels or simple lodging.

The shift in consumption patterns towards the leisure economy also occurs in almost all countries within the middle-class society. In addition, many companies will take advantage of this opportunity with the increasingly rapid development of technology, giving birth to the phenomenon of products or services sold through internet media. Traveloka is one of them that takes advantage of the phenomenon of the leisure economy and the products and services sold through the internet/online media so that Traveloka can become an intermediary between sellers and buyers as well as a forum for hotels in marketing their hotels. Researchers take the reason for choosing Traveloka research objects because Traveloka can make it easier for consumers to get the goods or services they want and can fulfill consumer desires that are formed due to the leisure economy. In the Traveloka application and the official Instagram, Traveloka always provides a place for consumers to provide a customer experience while using Traveloka. Traveloka itself is in great demand because Traveloka followers on Instagram have a lot of nearly 1 million followers, or 933 thousand to be precise.

The benefit of this research is that parties engaged in the business sector, especially in the field of e-commerce, know what factors can influence repurchase intention, both things that can increase it or can cause it to decrease or decrease. Based on that fact, these business actors can prepare strategies or innovate to maintain the existence of their business or company, considering that the growth of e-commerce in Indonesia is increasing and the competition is also getting higher due to human needs that can be met through e-commerce. However, e-commerce such as Traveloka has problems and problems that currently need to be addressed, namely a decrease in Traveloka website visits from time to time, as shown in Figure 2. following.

Source: Similar web, 2022

Figure 1. Visits from Time to Time (in million)

Visit the Traveloka website, when seen in Figure 2. has consistently decreased from time to time, starting from May 2022 to September 2022. The most significant decrease was from July to August, from 17.93 million visitors to only 16.02 million visitors. The lowest decline occurred from June to July, from 18.88 million visitors to 17.92 million visitors. The decrease in Traveloka visits by consumers could impact their repurchasing intentions to Traveloka because, with this decrease, it is assumed that there are consumers who do not visit the Traveloka website in the following month. This research is marketing research, but the theory that underlies this research is the theory of consumer behavior, namely the theory of planned behavior, because, in general, consumer purchasing decisions for a product are influenced by various factors. One is consumer behavior, in this case, purchasing decisions influenced by purchase intentions. In (I. Ajzen, 1991) the proximal determinant of behavior is the intention to behave, which, in turn, is determined by attitudes, subjective norms & perceived behavioral control.

Attitude towards refers to the level of positive or negative evaluation or individual assessment of behavioral performance. Attitudes are based on salient behavioral beliefs and outcome evaluations. Behavioral beliefs refer to the perceived likelihood of an expected outcome occurring due to involvement in certain behaviors. Assessment of results involves assessing the possible consequences of certain behaviors (Meitiana, 2017). The factor of the Theory of Planned Behavior is that this attitude ultimately influences consumers in booking hotel rooms. If the price of a hotel room is ordered far in advance, the one ordered closer to D-day will be more expensive closer to the D-day caused of high fixed costs, here the role of attitude influences where the negative consequences of ordering a hotel room close to D-day will be expensive so that it raises an attitude that will book a hotel room in advance. As an example of a factor from the Theory of Planned Behavior, namely subjective norms, there is a co-worker who reviews at a hotel that is currently viral, and we are interested in staying there because of the desire to imitate this co-worker which is expected to increase his social status to generate emotional buying.

Traveloka seeing the size of the Indonesian market launched Traveloka Experience, developed from pre-existing activity features. The Traveloka Experience provides 12 product categories, from attraction tickets, to cinemas, spas, sports, theme parks, hotels, and others. Not only domestic entertainment, but Traveloka has also expanded its products by collaborating with 4,000 partners spread across 60 countries. This feature also strengthens Traveloka's position as a technology company that has grown to seven Southeast Asia and Australian governments. Traveloka is the leading discovery platform in Southeast Asia because it has been downloaded more than 40 million times with more than 35 million active users every month (M., P., A. Hafiz, 2019). According

to the release of (B. Millward, 2016) as of mid-2016, the growth rate for Traveloka's brand value (brand potential) was the highest, namely 33 percent. Traveloka outperformed two popular online buying and selling sites in Indonesia: Tokopedia (22 percent) and Bukalapak (15 percent). Traveloka is recognized as the strongest brand in the online sector, with a Brand Contribution value of more than 60 percent (A., M. Hasan, 2016). The key for the brand value to grow is advertising. Referring to Adensity data in (A., M. Hasan, 2016) throughout 2015, Traveloka allocated funds of IDR 631 billion for advertising services on 13 national television stations. Traveloka ads get the most significant among other travel sites; it's no longer surprising. According to e-Marketer data in (A., M. Hasan, 2016) sales profits for online travel sites this year reached \$5.97 billion, equivalent to Rp.78 trillion. This figure increased from \$4.26 billion in 2014 to \$5 billion in 2015 (Hasan, 2016). These advantages are significant for the company's long-term sustainability, so the company must pay attention to its long-term sales, in this case, the intention to repurchase by consumers and customers.

Based on the issues, phenomena, problems, and gaps of previous research, as well as the significance of variables, this study entitled "The Influence of Brand Image, Customer Engagement and Web Design Quality on Online Repurchase Intentions Mediated by Electronic Trust in Hotel Reservations on the Traveloka Application (Study on Traveloka in Malang City)." This research is expected to explain the effect of brand image, customer involvement, and web design quality on online repurchase intentions mediated by electronic trust variables.

2. Materials and Methods

The type of research used in this study is explanatory or explanatory research using a quantitative approach. The reason for using this analytical tool is because the quantitative approach is a type of research whose specifications are systematic, planned, and structured from the start to the creation of the research design. This research aims to examine and explain the influence of brand image, website design quality, and customer involvement on online repurchase intentions directly and indirectly by mediating electronic trust in hotel reservations on the Traveloka application. The research location in this study is in Malang Raya in 2022. Malang Raya was chosen because Malang City is one of the cities in East Java Province, the largest after Surabaya City, both in terms of area and population. The population in this study are Traveloka Application consumers who have used Traveloka in Malang Raya, the hotels in question are all hotels in Indonesia. As for the sample from the calculation of 10 x 17 statement indicators in the questionnaire, the number of respondents was 170 people. Thus the number of pieces is assumed to be able to provide accurate data so that the research results can be closer to reality.

The type of data used in this study is primary data collected directly in the field by researchers conducting research. This study's preliminary data was obtained from respondents' answers through a questionnaire. The data collection technique used in this study was the questionnaire method. In this study, the questionnaire was handed over to respondents, namely Traveloka users in Malang Raya. Dissemination or distribution of questionnaires was carried out to someone who had made a hotel reservation through Traveloka and met the criteria set by the researcher. The distribution of questionnaires in this study was carried out online and offline so that the distribution of questionnaires could be carried out efficiently. This quantitative study uses a questionnaire as a data collection instrument, so a pilot test is needed. The pilot test in this study aims to determine the research instrument's feasibility by testing the device's validity and reliability. The analysis technique used in this study is to employ descriptive analysis and inferential analysis methods. All stages of data analysis were carried out using the linearity program SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Science)

for Windows version 26.0 and Smart Modeling Partial Least Squares version 3.0. The purpose of data analysis is essential to simplify data into a form that is easier to read and interpret. Provisions for testing the hypothesis are carried out by resampling bootstrapping. The statistical test used is the t-test with a critical number of t-statistics > t-table with a significance level of 0.05 (5%) so that the proposed hypothesis is accepted. Testing the mediation hypothesis can be done by testing the intervention of the mediating variable. The proposed conceptual framework is shown in Figure 3 following:

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 The Effect of Brand Image on Online Repurchase Intentions

The research results show that brand image significantly influences online repurchase intentions; this can be interpreted that the higher the idea of a brand, the higher the picture, and the online repurchase intention will also increase. Providing quality assurance, quality, and certainty for consumers can be used to convince a customer to make a repeat purchase. The results of this study are significant because the image of the Traveloka brand in consumers' minds makes consumers confident about making hotel reservation transactions. After all, consumers feel they have used an application brand that already has an image in their field so that it will not bring harm to consumers. The significant influence of brand image on online repurchase intention is inseparable from the support of each indicator. The consumer benefit indicator has the most crucial role in brand image. Benefits for consumers talk about the quality of service that consumers expect and provide products that match the benefits that consumers expect. In the current digital era, information about benefits for consumers is straightforward to find and compare with one another, so benefits for consumers are an essential concern for Traveloka because the product image of a brand informs, inspires, entertains, influences, and destroys a choice. Make it easier for consumers to research products or services.

The results of this study support image theory, a series of knowledge, experiences, feelings (emotions), and judgments organized in the human cognition system or personal knowledge that is strongly believed to be accurate. In addition, according to (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) interest is formed by two things: a subjective norm associated with individual perceptions and beliefs about a brand and the influence of other people who start a brand image in the minds of these individuals. Someone who

has a good perception of a brand and gets good power from other individuals will strengthen the individual's interests and reasons for choosing and using products from that brand, and vice versa; this means that the better the brand image is formed in the minds of consumers, the more consumers feel proud and satisfied in using the product, and the stronger the confidence of consumers to remain loyal which will have an impact on repurchasing interest. The results of this study support research conducted by (Wijaya, F. & Sugiono, 2015) where the influence of brand image on repurchase intentions states that brand image has a positive impact on purchase intentions. This research is different from the research object of (Wijaya, F. & Sugiono, 2015) namely Pond's, so this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of brand image on repurchase intentions.

3.2 The Effect of Brand Image on Electronic Trust

The study results show that brand image significantly affects electronic trust; this means that image can increase confidence in the Traveloka brand. The idea is that the Traveloka brand can convince consumers that all the information submitted is correct. The results of this study are significant because Traveloka's brand image makes consumers feel safe to establish a relationship and trust the brand; this happens with the support of each indicator, namely popularity, benefits for consumers, and social status. The descriptive analysis results show that consumer benefits are the most important indicator of brand image. This indicates that consumers assess Traveloka's brand image by looking at how these consumers see the benefits of the product. Benefits for consumers talk about the quality of service that consumers expect and provide products that match the benefits that consumers expect. In the current digital era, information about benefits for consumers is straightforward to find and compare with one another, so benefits for consumers are an essential concern for Traveloka because the product image of a brand informs, inspires, entertains, influences, and destroys a belief.

Researchers have conducted open interviews with respondents' representatives through questions related to why they (Traveloka consumers) pay attention to brand image and get the result that well-known product brands make it seem as if consumers have become trusted, especially in terms of product or service quality, service, and quality. Price. Furthermore, in terms of benefits for consumers, what is no less important is how to provide appropriate products to provide consumers with the help that consumers expect. This will make consumers feel more confident and willing to trust the brand. Another indicator of brand image that contributes to a significant influence on electronic trust is social status. Its social status includes giving consumers an impression of class compared to similar products. The social quality of a brand will convince consumers to place their trust in brands with good representation. Meanwhile, the brand image indicator, namely popularity, is the indicator with the lowest value even though it still has a reasonable interpretation because online travel agent companies that are popular in Indonesia are not only Traveloka. Even though Traveloka continues to progress to gain market share that continues to grow in Indonesia, in reality, other online travel agents are also popular in Indonesia and abroad. Hence, consumers sometimes switch to other online travel agents.

The results of this study are also in line with the findings of previous research conducted by (Semuel & Adi, S., 2014) brand image obtained by consumers has an impact on trust because when the brand can create a sense of confidence in the services expected by consumers. If consumers have yet to experience a product or a brand image, they tend to trust brands they like or are well-known (F., P. Musay, 2013). The object of this research is different from the research object of (Semuel & Adi,

S., 2014) namely smartphone products, so that this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of brand image on trust.

3.3 *The Effect of Customer Engagement on Online Repurchase Intentions*

The research results show that customer involvement significantly influences online repurchase intentions; this can be interpreted that the higher the participation of a customer, the online repurchase intention will also increase. Providing quality assurance, quality, and certainty for consumers can be used to convince a customer to make a repeat purchase. The results of this study are significant because the involvement of Traveloka customers in the minds of consumers makes consumers confident about making hotel reservation transactions. After all, consumers feel they have participated in the application brand, which has allowed them to participate in the brand's progress.

The significant influence of customer involvement on online repurchase intentions is inseparable from the support of each indicator. Passion and enthusiasm indicators have the most critical role in customer engagement. Passion talks about a strong relationship between the customer and the product/service provider company. A customer with power for a company will describe their relationship as irreplaceable and even considered a suitable partner. Enthusiasm reflects the level of excitement and customer interest in a brand. Strong relationships between customers and product/service provider companies will only last for a while in the digital era. Researchers have conducted open interviews with representatives of respondents through questions related to why they (Traveloka consumers) pay attention to customer involvement and get the result that by establishing consumer interactions with service providers or between consumers, consumers get reviews that match the reality on the ground by joining the Traveloka user community.

The results of this study support Perkins (2014) in his book entitled "The Community Manager's Playbook - How to Build Brand Awareness and Customer Engagement," saying that there are six customer journey processes to become part of a brand. The six points are Awareness, Discovery, Attraction, Interaction, Purchase, and Advocacy. Audience satisfaction with a product or service he tried will make him go even further to the purchase stage. At this stage, the audience has made a purchase. A consumer who is well involved with a brand and gets a good influence from that involvement will strengthen the individual's interest and reason for choosing and using the product, and vice versa; this means that the better the customer involvement formed by online travel agents, then consumers will be interested at anything related to the online travel agent and the stronger the confidence of consumers to remain loyal which will have an impact on the emergence of repurchasing interest.

The results of this study support previous research on customer engagement, mainly focusing on the relationship between customer involvement and repurchase intention, and concluded that customer engagement has a direct and significant relationship with customer repurchase intention; research states that the strength of this relationship depends on the level of how much the customer is satisfied with the output of their engagement experience (Roushdy, A. & Ali, 2015). The object of this research is different from the research object of (Roushdy, A. & Ali, 2015) namely the Takaful Insurance Industry, so this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of customer involvement on repurchase intentions.

3.4 *The Effect of Customer Engagement on Electronic Trust*

The results of the study show that customer involvement has a significant effect on electronic trust, this means that involvement can increase trust in the Traveloka brand. The involvement felt by Traveloka customers can convince consumers that all the information submitted is correct. The results of this study are significant because Traveloka's customer involvement makes consumers feel safe to establish a relationship and place their trust in the brand, this happens with the support of each indicator, namely passion, enthusiasm, interaction and identification.

The results of the descriptive analysis show that passion and enthusiasm are the most important indicators of customer engagement. This indicates that consumers assess Traveloka's customer engagement by looking at how these customers are involved with their products. Passion talks about a strong relationship between the customer and the product provider company. A customer who has a passion for a company will describe their relationship as something that is irreplaceable and even considered as a suitable partner. Enthusiasm reflects the level of excitement and customer interest in a brand.

In the current digital era, strong relationships between customers and product/service provider companies will not last long, so passion and enthusiasm are an important concern for Traveloka because with passion and enthusiasm a customer can inform, inspire, entertain, influence, and destroy a trust. Furthermore, in terms of passion and enthusiasm, what is no less important is how to make customers become part of Traveloka when talking about the Traveloka application and getting customers excited when discussing the Traveloka application. This will make consumers feel more confident and willing to put their trust in the brand. Another indicator of customer engagement that contributes to a significant influence on electronic trust is identification. Identification includes the success of Traveloka is the success of customers. Identification of a brand will convince consumers to place their trust in brands that have good participation.

Meanwhile, the indicator of customer involvement, namely Interaction, is the indicator with the lowest score even though it still has a good interpretation. This happens because sometimes in community discussions on the Traveloka application, in general, not everyone has the same opinion. Even though Traveloka provides a separate platform for the community that functions to filter out inappropriate comments, in reality more people use platforms other than those provided by Traveloka which are more frequently used, so that sometimes consumers debate without a clear end without an intermediary from Traveloka. The results of this study are also in line with the findings of previous studies where high involvement indicates higher customer trust in the company in an interaction relationship (So, K., K., F., King & Sparks, B., 2014). The object of this research is different from that of (So, K., K., F., King & Sparks, B., 2014) namely the Takaful Insurance Industry, so that this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of customer involvement on repurchase intentions.

3.5 *The Effect of Web Design Quality on Online Repurchase Intentions*

The results of the research conducted show that the quality of web design has a significant influence on online repurchase intentions. this can be interpreted that the higher the quality of a web design, the intention to repurchase online will also increase. Providing quality assurance, quality and certainty for consumers can be used to convince a customer to make a repeat purchase. The results of this study are significant because the quality of the design of the Traveloka web in the minds of consumers makes consumers confident about making hotel reservation transactions because the web

is felt to have a quality design in the application brand that is of good quality in terms of pages and appearance.

The significant influence of web design quality on online repurchase intentions is inseparable from the support of each indicator. Privacy or privacy indicators have the most important role in the quality of web design. Privacy or privacy talks about consumers feeling that consumer privacy is protected on this site. Consumers will feel safe transacting with this site. The current digital era is not necessarily risky, on the contrary, all information that is contained in the digital realm can actually be spread, and usually information that is spread directly in bulk, so it is necessary to pay attention to consumer privacy.

Researchers have conducted open interviews with representatives of respondents through questions related to why they (Traveloka consumers) pay attention to the quality of web design and get the result that a web design that is easy to operate will make transactions faster and easier for those who are unfamiliar with online travel agents to learn. (I. Ajzen, 1991) theory of planned behavior (TPB) to explain and predict the process of e-commerce adoption by consumers. The process is captured through two online consumer behaviors: (1) obtaining information and (2) purchasing products from web vendors. A website from a brand that looks good quality design and also gets a good influence from the quality of the design will strengthen the individual's interest and reasons for choosing and using the product, and vice versa, this means that the better the quality of the web design made online travel agent, consumers will feel that their privacy is protected in making transactions on the online travel agent application and the stronger the consumer's confidence to remain loyal, which will have an impact on repurchasing interest.

The results of this study are also in line with the findings of previous research on web design quality, especially focusing on the relationship between web design quality and repurchase intention in research conducted by (Wilson & Keni., 2018) who found that website design quality influences customer intention to repurchase a company. (repurchase intention). Furthermore, research conducted by (Siagian & Cahyono, 2014) found that the quality of website design positively influences repurchase intentions. The object of this research is different from the research object of (Siagian & Cahyono, 2014) namely online shops, so this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of web design quality on repurchase intentions.

3.6 The Effect of Web Design Quality on Electronic Trust

The results of the study show that the quality of web design has a significant effect on electronic trust; this can be interpreted that the rate of innovation can increase confidence in the Traveloka brand. The design quality on webTraveloka can convince consumers that all the information submitted is correct. The results of this study are significant because the quality of Traveloka's web design makes consumers feel safe to surf the web and trust the brand; this happens with the support of each indicator, namely efficiency or efficiency, system availability or system availability, fulfillment or compliance. And privacy or privacy.

The results of the descriptive analysis show that privacy is the most critical indicator of web design quality. This indicates that consumers judge the quality of Traveloka's web design by looking at how secure these customers are with the quality of their products. Privacy or privacy talks about consumers feeling that consumer privacy is protected on this site. Consumers will feel safe transacting with this site. Privacy is an essential concern for Traveloka because, with privacy, a customer can inform, inspire, entertain, influence, and destroy trust.

Furthermore, regarding privacy, what is no less important is how to make customers feel safe in transactions with the Traveloka application; this will make consumers feel more confident and willing to put their trust in the brand. The current digital era is not necessarily risky; on the contrary, all information in the digital realm can be spread. Usually, data is applied directly in bulk, so paying attention to consumer privacy is necessary. Another indicator of web design quality that significantly influences electronic trust is system availability or system availability. System availability or system availability includes the Traveloka Application not having errors or crashes at any time. System availability or the availability of a web system will convince consumers to place their trust in brands that have good design advantages. Another indicator of web design quality that contributes to a significant influence on electronic trust is fulfillment. Fulfillment includes the Traveloka Application, which allows reservation changes and cancellations. Satisfaction or completion of a web will convince consumers to trust brands with good design advantages.

Meanwhile, the web design quality indicator, namely efficiency, is the indicator with the lowest score, even though it still has a reasonable interpretation. This happens because sometimes the Traveloka application loads slowly. Even though Traveloka provides sufficient servers to prevent mass users from using it simultaneously, in reality, not all users' internet speed is the same; there are still many who use the Traveloka Application in remote areas, so sometimes consumers experience slow internet on the Traveloka Application. The results of this study are also in line with the findings of previous research where (Wilson & Keni., 2018) stated that the quality of website design owned by a page has a significant impact on building trust in the minds of consumers towards the company. The object of this research is different from the research object of (Wilson & Keni., 2018) namely the Indonesian e-commerce industry, so that this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of web design quality on trust.

3.7 Effects of Electronic Trust on Online Repurchase Intentions

The results of the research conducted show that electronic trust has a significant effect on online repurchase intentions, this can be interpreted that the higher the trust through electronic media, the online repurchase intention will also increase. Providing quality assurance, quality and certainty for consumers can be used to convince a customer to make a repeat purchase. The results of this study are significant because trust through electronic media such as Traveloka in the minds of consumers makes consumers confident about making hotel reservation transactions because electronic media is felt to have confidence in the minds of consumers, the brand of the application is safe in terms of data and transactions. The significant influence of electronic trust on online repurchase intentions is inseparable from the support of each indicator. The acceptability indicator has the most important role in electronic trust. Acceptability talks about the Application providing services that are well received and providing responsive services. In the current digital era, it is easier for people to refuse an offer because they do not meet face to face, so there is no shame in rejecting it, so it is necessary to pay attention to consumer acceptance.

The relationship between electronic trust and online repurchase intention is supported by the theory from (Kotler & Gary, 2012) which states that repurchase occurs because of loyalty and trust. An electronic media from a brand that is well trusted and gets a good influence from that trust will strengthen the individual's interest and reasons for choosing and using the product, and vice versa, this means that the better the electronic trust made by online travel agents, then consumers will feel able to rely on the online travel agent and the stronger the confidence of consumers to remain loyal which will have an impact on the emergence of repurchasing interest. The results of this study are

also in line with the findings of previous research on electronic trust, especially focusing on the relationship between electronic trust and repurchase intention in a study conducted by (CR. hinomona, 2013) which showed that customer trust positively influences repurchase intention. The object of this research is different from the research object of (CR. hinomona, 2013) namely an African context, so that this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of trust on repurchase intentions.

3.8 Effect of Brand Image on Online Repurchase Intentions through Electronic Trust

The results show that brand image has an important impact on online repurchase intentions through electronic trust. The results of this study are significant because the mediation impact of electronic trust is known to be partial mediation. Thus, electronic trust can bridge the influence of brand image on online repurchase intentions. Still, without electronic trust, Traveloka's brand image can increase consumers' online repurchase intention.

In line with (Hair, J., Black. W., Babin B., & Anderson R., 2019) that in the mediating variable, there is evidence of the intervention of the mediating variable, which states that if (a), (b), and (c) are significant, then (c') is said to be a partial mediation variable, in this case, the correlation (a) shows the model examining the effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable, namely the effect of brand image on electronic trust, correlation (b) shows the examination of the influence of the mediating variable on the dependent variable, namely the effect of electronic trust on online repurchase intentions and correlation (c) shows the examination of the effect of the variable independent on the dependent variable directly or without going through a mediating variable, namely the effect of brand image on online repurchase intentions. The Traveloka brand image, which consists of popularity, benefits for consumers, and social status, makes consumers believe that the brand will not do anything harmful; this will be a consideration for consumers in the decision-making process to buy again at the next opportunity. In the current digital era, information regarding consumer benefits is elementary to find and compare with one another.

This study's results align with previous research conducted by (Rahmi, D. & Ahmad, 2017) who found that trust is a mediation effect of brand image on online purchase intentions. The impact of this trust mediation is known to be partial or partial mediation. The object of this research is the same as the research object of (Rahmi, D. & Ahmad, 2017) namely Traveloka so that brand image has a significant positive effect on online repurchase intentions through electronic trust in this study because it has the same research object.

3.9 The Effect of Customer Engagement on Online Repurchase Intentions Through Electronic Trust

The results show that customer engagement has an important impact on online repurchase intentions through electronic trust. This study's results are significant because electronic faith's mediation impact is known to be partial mediation. Thus, electronic trust can bridge the effect of customer involvement on repurchase intentions online. Still, without electronic faith basically, Traveloka's customer involvement can increase consumers' online repurchase intention. In line with (Hair, J. et al., 2019) that in the mediating variable there is evidence of the intervention of the mediating variable, which states that if (a), (b), and (c) are significant, then (c') is said to be a partial mediation variable, in this case, the correlation (a) shows the model examining the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable, namely the effect of customer involvement on

electronic trust, correlation (b) shows the examination of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable, namely the effect of electronic trust on online repurchase intentions and correlation (c) shows the examination of the effect of the variable independent of the dependent variable directly or without going through a mediating variable, namely the effect of customer involvement on online repurchase intentions.

Traveloka's customer involvement which consists of passion, enthusiasm, interaction, and identification makes consumers believe that the brand will not do anything detrimental; this will be a consideration for consumers in the decision-making process to buy again at the next opportunity. Strong relationships between customers and product/service provider companies will only last for a while in the digital era. This study's results align with previous research by (Rahmawati & Sanaji., 2015) who found that brand trust is a mediation effect of customer involvement on online repurchase intentions. The mediating impact of brand trust is known to be partial mediation. The object of this research is different from the research object of (Rahmawati & Sanaji., 2015) namely @XL123, so this research can strengthen and can expand research related to the effect of customer involvement on repurchase intentions mediated by trust..

3.10 Effects of Web Design Quality on Online Repurchase Intentions through Electronic Trust

The results show that web design quality has an important impact on online repurchase intentions through electronic trust. The results of this study are significant because the mediation impact of electronic trust is known to be partial mediation. Thus, electronic trust can bridge the influence of web design quality on online repurchase intentions. Still, web design quality Traveloka can increase consumers' online repurchase intentions without electronic trust. In line with (Hair, J. et al., 2019) that in the mediating variable, there is evidence of the intervention of the mediation variable, which states that if (a), (b), and (c) are significant, then (c') is said to be a partial mediation variable, in this case, the correlation (a) shows the model examining the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable, namely the effect of web design quality on electronic trust, correlation (b) shows the examination of the influence of the mediating variable on the dependent variable, namely the effect of electronic trust on online repurchase intentions and correlation (c) shows the examination of the influence the independent variable on the dependent variable directly or without going through a mediating variable, namely the effect of web design quality on online repurchase intentions.

The quality of Traveloka's web design which consists of efficiency or efficiency, system availability or system availability, fulfillment or fulfillment, and privacy or privacy makes consumers believe that the brand will not do anything harmful; this will be a consideration for consumers in the decision-making process to repurchase at the next opportunity. The current digital era is not necessarily risky; on the contrary, all information in the digital realm can be spread. Usually, knowledge is applied directly in bulk, so paying attention to consumer privacy is necessary. The results of this study align with previous research conducted by (Wilson & Keni., 2018) which found that trust acts as a mediation effect for the quality of website design on repurchase intentions. The impact of the mediation of trust is known as partial or partial mediation. The object of this research is different from the study of (Wilson & Keni., 2018) namely the Indonesian e-commerce industry, so that this research can strengthen and expand research related to the effect of web design quality on trust-mediated repurchase intentions.

4. Conclusion

This study examines and analyzes the effect of brand image, customer involvement, and web design quality on online repurchase intentions for hotel reservations in the Traveloka application through the mediation of electronic trust. Based on research results, it can be seen that: Brand image can increase repurchase intention online. The increasing brand image will have a significant effect on increasing the online repurchase intention of Traveloka consumers. Popularity, consumer benefits, and social status can be promoted optimally to grow consumers' online repurchase intentions. Brand image can increase electronic trust. The higher the brand image, the easier it is for salespeople to gain consumers' confidence. Benefits for consumers are essential in shaping the brand image of online travel agents, so it needs to be continuously developed to maintain consumer trust.

Customer engagement can increase repurchase intentions online. Increasing customer engagement will have a significant effect on increasing online repurchase intentions from Traveloka consumers. Passion, enthusiasm, interaction, and identification can be carried out optimally to foster consumers' online repurchase intentions. Customer engagement can increase electronic trust. The higher the customer involvement, the easier it is for online travel agents to gain the confidence of consumers. Passion and enthusiasm are the most critical factors in shaping customer involvement in online travel agents, so it needs to be continuously developed to maintain consumer confidence. Quality web design can increase repurchase intentions online.

The increasing quality of web design will significantly affect online repurchase intentions from Traveloka consumers. Efficiency or efficiency, system availability or system availability, fulfillment or fulfillment, and privacy or privacy can be implemented optimally to foster consumers' online repurchase intentions. Web design quality can increase electronic trust. The higher the quality of the web design, the easier it is for online travel agents to gain consumers' confidence. Privacy or privacy is the most critical factor in shaping the quality of online travel agent web design, so it needs to be continuously developed to maintain consumer trust. Electronic trust can drive an increase in repurchase intentions online.

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